

1 **Data sharing restrictions are hampering precision health in the European Union**

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21 Contemporary healthcare is undergoing a transition, shifting from a population-based approach to
22 personalized medicine on an individual level¹. In October 2023, a European Partnership for Personalized
23 Medicine was officially launched² to communicate its benefits to citizens and healthcare systems in member
24 countries. The main debate revolves around the inconsistency in regulatory changes within personal data
25 access and its potential commercialization. Moreover, the lack of unified consensus within EU countries is
26 leading to problems with data sharing to progress personalized medicine. This commentary will discuss the
27 integration of biological data with personal information on a European scale for the advancement of
28 personalized medicine, raising legal considerations of data protection under the EU General Data Protection
29 Regulation (GDPR)³.

30 Personalized medicine is a data-driven approach, where ‘big data’ and its accessibility are of key importance.
31 Big data can be based on epidemiological information and increasingly on omics data⁴, particularly genomics,
32 transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics. When omics profiles are integrated with clinical data, an
33 individual’s molecular makeup can be studied. However, compliance with the GDPR, along with varying
34 country-specific interpretations, presents obstacles to the deposition of health-related omics data.
35 Additionally, most repositories operate beyond EU borders, in the USA, UK, and Japan. There is a pressing
36 need for a GDPR-approved data repository within EU borders to streamline omics-driven personalized
37 medicine.

38 In Denmark, every person is assigned a unique civil registration number (CPR), which grants access to
39 general practitioners, hospitals, and pharmacies. It also links national databases containing diagnoses,
40 laboratory data, and socioeconomic information. Such data are securely stored in government-protected
41 databases and may only be accessed through preapproved channels by the Danish Health Data Authority.
42 These extremely sensitive data serve as a powerful resource for science⁵ but also pose a potential
43 vulnerability if misused. The introduction of the GDPR in 2018 has provided an additional layer of security
44 but has also sparked numerous discussions on how to define unidentifiable datasets. Hence, there is a need
45 for common agreement on whether pseudonymized data⁶ and personal omics data like genomics, can be
46 shared within repositories or between EU countries. The management of research omics data, adhering to
47 FAIR principles, requires a balance within the notion of “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”⁷.
48 Data subjects must be well-informed and consent to the use of personal data, and they should have the
49 right to withdraw consent at any time. Safeguarding data subjects' rights while harnessing the potential of
50 omics data for healthcare is the central concern in this evolving field.

51 For clinical practice, the GDPR has generated an additional layer of complexity but has also prompted
52 fundamental rethinking of data security and protection of privacy as a human right. Personally identifiable
53 information has the potential to negatively impact not only the individual but also their family by revealing
54 predispositions to severe conditions, substance abuse, and more. Even across a small country like Denmark,
55 interpretations of the GDPR differ, and more so across Europe. Development of more efficient treatments
56 requires increasingly detailed data on patients, such as combining patient-level data from industry-
57 sponsored randomized controlled trials and public real-world data. This is challenging because the data
58 reside in different systems and cannot be transferred between the structures without full anonymization.
59 In academia, mainly due to the lack of clear guidelines, the GDPR initially caused long delays in approvals,
60 where researchers faced issues with temporary contracts and time-limited grants. At this time of writing,
61 EU researchers cannot deposit data according to FAIR principles, which has also complicated submissions to
62 some journals. This remains an issue for academia, emphasizing the importance of international
63 cooperation to address these challenges.

64 Legally, the first step towards overcoming these barriers is the harmonization of GDPR interpretation and
65 application across member states (**Figure 1**). The final word on GDPR interpretation resides with the EU Court
66 of Justice. However, case law development is slow, and to save time, common guidelines and frameworks
67 are needed. These guidelines should provide clarity on crucial GDPR terms such as 'explicit consent',
68 'necessary for the performance of a contract', and 'legitimate interests'. In that regard, the forthcoming
69 European Health Data Space (EHDS) could play an important role⁸ in promoting uniformity across member
70 states, reduce discrepancies in GDPR interpretation, and serve as a platform for resolving disputes related to
71 health data sharing. This approach could reduce the bureaucratic burden associated with cross-border data
72 sharing and make the process more efficient.

73 On the technical front, encryption, pseudonymization, and anonymization techniques that protect health
74 data during transmission and storage are necessary. Emerging technologies such as differential privacy and
75 homomorphic encryption can further enhance data protection by allowing the sharing and analysis of health
76 data without revealing sensitive information. Blockchain technology, in combination with interactive AI,
77 could also be utilized to facilitate informed consent and create a transparent record of data transactions,
78 preventing unauthorized access and modifications⁹. Secure platforms should use standardized data formats
79 and robust Application Programming Interfaces to enable seamless and secure data exchange.

80 Denmark boasts a strong tradition in register-based research⁵. A solution that works nationwide is facilitated
81 by a publicly owned service, 'The Research Machine'¹⁰. This platform allows researchers to upload data and

82 link it to a wide array of registers connected to the individual CPR number. After acquiring proper approvals
83 from the ethical and data protection committees, users can access an online environment to conduct
84 analyses using R, Python, SPSS, among others. To protect highly personal information, Research Machine
85 users are prohibited from exporting or sharing individual-level data. The Research Machine comes with some
86 limitations, including the export of plots and tables that may disclose individual-level data points, such as
87 scatter plots. Another challenge, particularly in rapidly evolving fields like omics data analysis, is the reliance
88 on system owners for updating and installing software and packages, as users lack this capability. Moreover,
89 although the Research Machine is a nationwide service, it is not currently possible to share uploaded data
90 between projects. Hence, there is a need to establish national connections, followed by federated databases
91 within EU.

92 In conclusion, a combinatory approach of legal harmonization, novel technical solutions, streamlined
93 bureaucracy, and effective use of the EHDS throughout the complex national and international regulations
94 is required to overcome the barriers set by the GDPR to data sharing. While this requires substantial
95 cooperation and effort from all member states, it is a necessary step towards leveraging the full potential of
96 health and omics data for improving healthcare outcomes across the EU, always keeping in mind the need
97 for individual data protection.

98

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137 **Figures:**

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139 **Figure.1. Steps and solutions to share data across the EU member states for precision health**
140 AI-Artificial Intelligence; APIs- Application Programming Interfaces; GDPR- General Data Protection
141 Regulation; EHDS- European Health Data Space; EOSC - European Open Science Cloud; EP PerMed -
142 European Partnership for Personalized Medicine; EU – European Union; RM – Research Machine.
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